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Review Article

Advancing urban soil health: challenges, knowledge gaps, and future research perspectives

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HIGHLIGHTS

- Urban soils are under-researched compared to agricultural soils near cities.
- Studies focus on topsoil chemistry, ignoring deeper, physical, and biological aspects.
- Urban soil health studies are uneven and rarely examine links to human health.
- Linking soil experts with urban planners helps guide sustainable city development.
- Balanced soil health metrics are key to urban sustainability strategies.

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ABSTRACT

Urbanization is projected to surpass 65% of the global population by 2050 and urban soils remain an overlooked yet crucial component for a sustainable development.

Here we present an analysis of the current state of research on urban soil health, focusing specifically on soils embedded within strictly urban environments (urban-affected soils).

Based on scientific literature review, this study systematically investigates 63 scientific papers published between 2008 and early 2025, examining various aspects of soil health research in urban environment including geographical distribution, land use, sampling depths, and soil health indicators. The results indicate a growing interest in urban soil health, particularly in recent years. The prevalence of research on this topic in specific regions of the world may be the result of the distribution of metropolitan areas, with the consequent enhance of awareness and importance of soil health in those regions.

The emphasis on chemical properties, particularly soil contamination, in the literature is consistent with historical trends, while the limited attention given to physical and biological properties calls for a more balanced approach. Ecosystem services, despite their recognized importance, are underutilized, urging a deeper exploration of specific services that contribute directly to human health. Sampling depth at soil profile scale emerged as a crucial factor, with a significant proportion of studies limited to the topsoil at depths of 20 cm or less. Considering the correlation between soil depth and ecosystem services, the findings emphasize the need for future research to explore greater sampling depths for a more comprehensive understanding of urban soil health.

Despite the growing interest in the field, urban soil health research remains shallow, both literally and conceptually. This work highlights the need for stronger collaboration between soil scientists and urban stakeholders, such as policymakers, planners, and the citizens. Bridging this communication gap will help shape research agendas and policies that address urban challenges, inform planning, and promote sustainable development.

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1. Introduction

1.1. Urban soil health: challenges and opportunities

In the 1990s, urban soils were not yet a pedological object attracting the curiosity of scientists and city planners – far from it! At the time, they were often described as “non-soil,” materials of little interest from a pedological perspective, serving merely as substrates for human activity rather than as potentially fertile media for biodiversity (Craul, 1992). However, with the rise of sustainable development, urban soil science has gradually gained legitimacy and importance at local, national, European, and global scales. Over the last thirty years, this field has become essential for understanding the great diversity of urban soils (Morel et al., 2005), thereby enabling better integration of soil health into urban planning strategies.

Urban environments host a diverse range of soils within limited areas, marked by significant spatial heterogeneity and strong human influence. Unlike natural ecosystems, urban soils often lack spatial logic, combining deeply degraded, heavily modified, and minimally altered pseudo-natural soils (Effland & Pouyat, 1997; Morel et al., 2015). This variability derives from the diverse and dynamic land-use activities in cities and the frequent changes in land-use purposes along anthroposequences (Libessart et al., 2022; Norra & Stuben, 2003).

Urban soils are often composed of highly altered and manipulated materials, described as artefacts or technic materials (El Khalil et al., 2008; Pouyat et al., 2020). These soils display pronounced heterogeneity at both vertical and horizontal scales, influencing their physical, chemical, and biological properties (Craul, 1992; Morel et al., 2005). Common features include coarse texture, high bulk density, alkaline pH, and frequent contamination from human activities such as industrial emissions and traffic pollutants (Burghardt et al., 2015; Cornu et al., 2021; El Khalil et al., 2013; Joimel et al., 2016). Consequently, they typically exhibit low physical and chemical fertility, though some are engineered to support plant growth and biomass production, as in gardens, green roofs, and constructed Technosols (Schwartz et al., 1999; Séré et al., 2008; WRB-FAO, 2015).

Urban green areas, parks, green belts, urban agriculture plots, and other vegetated spaces, are the soils closest to citizens and yet paradoxically among the least studied. Most knowledge on soil health (SH) indicators derives from agricultural contexts, leaving urban environments underrepresented (Sapkota et al., 2021). Assessing soil health in urban contexts differs fundamentally from agricultural or grassland soils, which are generally more homogeneous and managed to support multiple ecosystem services, with production playing a prominent role. In urban soils, production is typically not a concern, yet many other ecosystem services, such as climate and water regulation, remain highly important. These soils therefore require indicators that capture their pronounced spatial heterogeneity, diverse origins, and vulnerability to human disturbances. According to the new EU soil law proposal Soil Monitoring and Resilience (Soil Monitoring Law) (COM/2023/416 final), SH is defined as “the physical, chemical, and biological condition of the soil determining its capacity to function as a vital living system and to provide ecosystem services.” Well-maintained urban soils can indeed provide ecosystem services (ESs) for human well-being comparable to those of agricultural and forest soils (Anne et al., 2018), thereby contributing to biodiversity and global health.

To comprehend the complexity of urban soils in the context of sustainable development requires close attention to urban management practices and their effects on SH indicators, as well as recognition of their ecological value and the preservation of their functions. Moreover, assessments must account for urban fragmentation, defined as the isolation of soil patches caused by urbanization and sealing, which negatively affects both soil health and soil functionalities (Seifollahi-Aghmiuni et al., 2022; Vieillard et al., 2024).

1.2. Importance of urban soil health

Worldwide, the urban population is projected to surpass 65 % of the total population by 2050 (United Nations, 2018). In the most developed countries, this figure will be notably higher, with Europe expected to increase from the current 73 % to 80 % (U.N., 2018). The escalation of urbanization poses a threat to global sustainable development, impacting both developed regions and those undergoing accelerated urbanization processes (Pauchard et al., 2006; Wang et al., 2023). This trend brings significant environmental challenges, particularly affecting soils. Therefore, assessing and enhancing urban SH has become critical for global health and sustainable urban planning.

Urban soil management practices should account for the unique conditions of these systems, adapting techniques from agriculture and forestry to the urban context. Practices such as soil engineering (e.g., construction of soils from wastes and by-products of urban activities) and de-sealing can restore or enhance ecological functions, improving soils’ capacity to provide ecosystem services (Fabbri et al., 2021).

Beyond ecosystem functioning, urban plant and soil microbiomes interact directly with human health. Studies show that exposure to diverse environmental microbiota can influence immune regulation and reduce risks of inflammatory disease (Liddicoat et al., 2020; Mills et al., 2020). Recognizing these intertwined relationships between urban soils, vegetation, and human well-being underscores the broader societal value of SH.

Despite the growing scientific interest, significant gaps remain in understanding how urbanization affects SH. This review specifically addresses soils embedded within strictly urban environments (urban-affected soils), examining their diversity, the challenges they face, and the knowledge gaps that require further study. Through a systematic approach, we aim to trace the trajectory of SH research in urban environments and highlight avenues for future research.

2. Materials and methods

2.1. Literature search and selecting criteria

We performed a literature search to gain an overview of soil health in urban ecosystems. The search used the terms of “soil health” and “urban” into the title, abstract, and keywords of the literature gathered via the Web Of Science (WOS) database. In addition, we focus our search on articles that were exclusively written in English, between 1980 and 2025 in peer-reviewed journals. We excluded meeting abstracts, conference reviews and conference proceedings.

The bibliometric analysis performed in this study followed the protocol established by the Collaboration for Environmental Evidence (CEE) as defined by Pullin et al. (2022). After reading all papers, we applied an additional criteria aiming to select only studies focusing on urban soils not intended for standard agricultural production. We applied this criterion because, after an initial analysis, we noticed that most of the papers focused on SH evaluation in standard agricultural farms located near urban areas (periurban environment). Including these papers would have created an artifact when analysing soil health in urban soils. Additionally, the management practices associated with these soils closely resemble those of traditional agricultural soils, and the existing literature already offers a plethora of information on urban agriculture (Azunre et al., 2019; Bidar et al., 2020; De Bon et al., 2009; Orsini et al., 2013; Quon, 1999; Tinsley, 2003). Consequently, we determined that these “agriculture” scenarios were misleading for evaluating SH in urban soils.

As outcome of this criteria, our selection included studies conducted in open fields or greenhouses, studies focusing on stakeholder engagement, studies connection soil health and water management and green infrastructure.

2.2. Screening and data analysis

Our bibliometric search identified a total of 217 articles. The procedure for the subsequent selection is illustrated in Fig. 1. After applying the exclusion criteria, 63 articles were included.

To understand the state of research on SH in urban contexts and explore the evolution of the theme, we summarize the information contained in the scientific papers, focusing on the following characteristics: geographic origin of the study, land use and vegetation type, main topic explored, and the sampling depth.

For the criterion land use, we settled six categories, including “park” for urban parks; “roadside” for small plots of land at the edges of roads and green belts; “residential” for soils of occupied, abandoned, or demolished houses; “forest” for urban forests; “industrial” for soils of abandoned, demolished or in activity industries; and “open space” such as sports fields, playgrounds, schools, and university campuses. For vegetation cover, the specified categories were “grass”, “shrub”, and “tree”. Sampling depth was also recorded and eventually divided into categories per depth if specified. Additionally, the articles were grouped according to five main topics, namely “Soil pollution and remediation”; “Ecosystem services”; “Water management and green infrastructures”; “Soil Health assessment”; and “Stakeholder surveys and policies”.

Subsequently, we summarised the following information on the indicators and properties reported in the publications: (i) soil chemical properties (such as pH, soil organic matter, electrical conductivity), (ii) biological properties (such as cumulative soil respiration and enzymatic activities), (iii) physical properties (such as soil porosity, hydrology, texture, and structure), (iv) ecosystem services (such as carbon storage

and greenhouse gases regulation), and (v) SH indexes (typically empirical multiparametric equations, as Shannon or Simpson indexes).

3. Overview of key findings and research focus

In our analysis, we focused on the publication dates and locations while gathering valuable insights on land use, vegetation, and sampling depth. We took a close look at the indicators, categorized them to uncover patterns, and grouped the articles by the main topic the authors addressed. Our goal was to understand the current state of knowledge and connect it with historical contexts. From the scientific literature on soil health in urban environments examined, we selected 63 key articles focused on green areas, forming the basis of this analysis.

The oldest article we found dates to 2008 (Shi et al., 2008), and the 78 % of the selected articles were published after 2021 (Fig. 2), highlighting the recent interest that the topic of urban soil health has garnered (Pouyat et al., 2020). This data aligns with Sellami & Terribile (2023)’s findings regarding the soil health in agricultural systems and suggests a growing acknowledgment of soil’s significance within the scientific community.

Regarding the geographical origin of the papers included in this review which mentioned the geographical area ($n = 61$), approximately 38 % are from the American continent, followed by Asia with 33 %. Europe and Oceania contribute 23 % and 5 %, respectively. Notably, only one article originates from Africa, highlighting a gap in research from this region, as well as in Oceania. Regarding the European articles, 9 out of 14 were published after 2024, underlying once again the recent interest that the topic has raised. The trend just showed might be explained by the greater presence of metropolises in the American and Asian continents compared to their European and Oceanic counterparts (Ramos & Roca, 2015), as well as by higher awareness of soil health in these regions and comparatively lower research capacity or different priorities (e.g., food security) in developing countries.

When looking at the land use category (Table 1), open space were the most represented urban green ecosystems, appearing in 32 instances, followed by parks (26) and residential areas (23) among the 59 articles that specified the land use type. In terms of vegetation types, grass was the most studied with 48 instances, followed by trees (23) and shrubs (15).

Most of the selected articles comprise experimental studies or site characterizations with soil sample analyses. Sampling in urban contexts has widely been reported as complex due to soil disturbances (Downey et al., 2021; Galle et al., 2021). Urban soils often face compaction issues, exacerbated by the presence of obstacles (pipes, construction debris, or other infrastructure), complicating the data collection process (Downey et al., 2021; Galle et al., 2021; Howard et al., 2016). Moreover, space constraints make it difficult to bring in equipment or machinery to sample subsoils.

The distribution of sampling depths is shown in Fig. 3, revealing that out of 63 articles, 51 conducted sampling and/or specified the sampling depth. More than 70 % of them did not exceed a depth of 20 cm.

This is an interesting finding since ESS, which can be at the base of SH evaluation, are very much dependent by both topsoil and subsoil (Ellili-Bargaoui et al., 2021). For instance, in soil biological studies, it is common to focus on the first 10 cm, as this layer is often considered the most biologically active due to the higher concentration of root exudates, microbial activity, and organic matter (Fierer et al., 2007; Jones et al., 2009). However, while the first 10 cm are relevant for soil biological processes, focusing solely on this layer may neglect soil functions associated to deeper layers, such as water retention and carbon storage, which are also influenced by the subsoil layers (Lal, 2004). To this respect, the correlation between soil depth and ESS, as showed by Adhikari et al. (2022) and Greiner et al. (2017), accentuates the necessity of sampling beyond this threshold. This insight suggests a need for future research in urban contexts to expand sampling depths where feasible, accompanied by a description of the soil horizons of the

Fig. 1. Flowchart diagram depicting the article selection procedure (n represents the number of studies). After the initial search in WOS incorporating “soil health” and “urban”, 217 studies were identified. 63 studies were used in this review after applying the exclusion criteria.

Fig. 2. Numbers of the selected articles grouped per year.

territory. Such an increase can provide a detailed account of the ES provided by urban soils, facilitate their quantification and make their evaluation more accurate. Notably, two authors (Seboko et al., 2021; Streeter & Schilling, 2018) collected samples at depths greater than 120 cm.

The parameters outlined in Table 2 highlight a dominant focus on chemical properties (76 %) as primary indicators for evaluating soil health across scientific studies. Physical properties are reported in 60 % of the papers, biological properties in 44 %, SH indexes in 37 %, and proxies of one or more ES in only 33 %, reflecting historical preferences for chemical attributes (Bünemann et al., 2018; Cornu et al., 2021).

The limited emphasis on biological and physical properties, observed in only 4 and 7 out of all the articles pre-2020 respectively, is particularly noteworthy. Physical properties (e.g., bulk density) are critical for assessing soil compaction and its susceptibility to urbanization-induced alterations, while biological attributes respond quickly to disturbances (Buzzard et al., 2021) and play a crucial role in understanding degradation and the soil's capacity to provide ESs. Interestingly, when properties are combined into a SH-related indexes, biological properties play a dominant role (last column of Table 2).

This imbalance highlights the need for research to focus more on physical and biological properties, without neglecting chemical characteristics, promoting a more holistic approach that includes these underrepresented attributes.

ESs connected to soil are also underrepresented, assessed in only 33 % of studies. Over 80 % focus exclusively on primary productivity and their proxies, such as NDVI, with no reference to modelling procedures. This limited scope reduces the transferability of findings and emphasizes the need for research to identify and quantify a broader range of ESs that directly contribute to human health, aligning with the growing recognition of urban soils' role in supporting well-being (Schwarz et al., 2022).

Regarding SH indexes, two main approaches emerge: 1) parametric equations focusing on specific biological aspects of the soil, such as nematodes and the application of biodiversity indices (i.e., Simpson and Shannon); 2) and holistic testing methods, such as the Cornell Soil Health Test (CSHT) (Schindelbeck et al., 2008), which evaluates a broader spectrum of soil properties, encompassing biological, chemical, and physical factors. Both approaches offer a more comprehensive assessment of soil health.

4. An insight on research topics and knowledge gaps

Building on this understanding of soil health indicators, ecosystem services, and SH indexes, we also examined how research is clustered

across topics (Fig. 4). The most represented topics are soil pollution and remediation (37 %) and soil health assessment (30 %), followed by ecosystem services (14 %), water management and green infrastructure (11 %), and stakeholder surveys and policies (8 %). In the following subsections, we discuss the approaches, outcomes, knowledge gaps, and the relationship between each of this topic and soil health. We excluded "Stakeholder surveys and policies" from the analysis due to the limited availability of information and the novelty of the topic. Nonetheless, in the last section "Future Perspectives and Conclusions", we highlighted the key insights gained from the articles within this category.

4.1. Soil pollution and remediation

Current knowledge

Soil pollution is a critical environmental challenge, particularly in urban areas where human activities introduce contaminants that threaten both soil and human health. Heavy metals and organic compounds remain the best-studied pollutants, long recognized for their capacity to compromise SH and reduce ESs (Pouyat et al., 2020). More recently a broader spectrum of contaminants, including volatile organic compounds (VOCs), microplastics, PFAS, antibiotics and soil pathogens, has emerged, adding new complexity to the problem (Li et al., 2023; Sillo et al., 2024; Zhao et al., 2024a).

The origin and distribution of pollutants in urban soils are closely tied to human activity and land-use history. Industrial processes, vehicular emissions and legacy activities such as historical manufacturing or waste mismanagement are major contributors (Sillo et al., 2024; Tóth et al., 2023). For example, roadside soils are typically enriched in Cd, Pb and Zn due to vehicle emissions, while soils near smelting and processing facilities often show elevated polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbon (PAH) concentrations (Bandowe et al., 2021; Çomakli et al., 2018). Beyond these traditional contaminants, VOCs provide additional insight as both pollutants and indicators of microbial shifts in soils, while hotspots of antibiotic residues frequently appear in densely populated areas, driven by waste mismanagement and other anthropogenic inputs (Sillo et al., 2024; Zhao et al., 2024a). History also shapes contamination patterns, with sites linked to past industrial activity, heavy traffic or pre-1970 infrastructure often carrying persistent legacy pollutants such as Pb from lead-based paints (Libessart et al., 2022; Martin et al., 2023).

In response to soil degradation, increasing attention is given to nature-based solutions aimed at requalification, renaturation or ecological re-functionalisation of urban soils. Such approaches are already implemented in practice through soil engineering (soil construction) (Fabbri et al., 2021) and phytomanagement (Evangelou &

Table 1

Location, land-use and vegetation type of the selected articles. Where only the region, the country, or multiple countries are indicated, the authors did not specify the locations in more detail. "NA" indicates not available.

Authors	Location	Land use and vegetation type
Shi et al., 2008	Shenzhen, Guangdong, China	Parks and roadsides
Chen et al., 2015	Beijing, Beijing Municipality, China	Parks (grass)
Harvey et al., 2016	Boolaroo, New South Wales, Australia	Residential and open spaces (grass)
Howard et al., 2016	Detroit, Michigan, U.S.A.	Parks, residential and industrial (grass)
Rahman et al., 2016	NA	NA
Sax et al., 2017	Ithaca, New York, U.S.A.	Open spaces (grass, shrubs, trees)
Çomakli et al., 2018	Erzurum, Eastern Anatolia, Turkey	Forest (trees)
Streeter & Schilling, 2018	Iowa, U.S.A.	Open spaces (grass)
Wang et al., 2018	Shanghai, Shanghai Municipality, China	Parks
Bandowe et al., 2019	Jena, Thuringia, Germany	Open spaces (grass)
Pleshakova et al., 2019	Stepnoe, Low Volga, Russia	Open spaces
Sefati et al., 2019	Ahvaz, Khuzestan, Iran	Parks and forest (grass, shrubs, trees)
Gurjar et al., 2020	New Delhi, New Delhi, India	Open spaces (grass)
Yu et al., 2020	New York City, New York, U.S.A.	Roadsides (trees)
Bandowe et al., 2021	Almalyk, Tashkent Region, Uzbekistan	Industrial, open spaces (grass)
Buzzard et al., 2021	Tucson, Arizona, U.S.A.	Residential (grass)
Downey et al., 2021	New York City, New York, U.S.A.	Forest (trees)
Galle et al., 2021	Cambridge and Boston, Massachusetts, U.S.A.	Parks and roadsides (trees)
Pike et al., 2021	Highland Park, Illinois, U.S.A.	Forest (trees)
Sapkota et al., 2021	Lubbock, Texas, U.S.A.	Residential (grass)
Savanoor et al., 2021	Mohindergarh and Narnaul, Haryana, India	Open spaces (grass)
Seboko et al., 2021	Johannesburg Granite Dome, Gauteng, South Africa	Open spaces (grass)
Gómez-sagasti et al., 2021	Vitoria-Gasteiz, Basque Country, Spain	Parks (grass)
Ward et al., 2021	New York City, New York, U.S.A.	Parks (grass, shrubs, trees)
Abu-Shanab et al., 2022	NA	Greenhouse (grass)
Gómez-Brandón et al., 2022	Santiago de Compostela, Galicia, Spain	Parks, open spaces, forest (grass, shrubs, trees)
Pease et al., 2022	Ames, Iowa, U.S.A.	Open spaces (grass)
Schwarz et al., 2022	Los Angeles, California, U.S.A.	NA
Ahmad & Rizvi, 2023	Neom, Tabuk, Saudi Arabia	NA
Balacco et al., 2023	Jersey City, New Jersey, U.S.A.	Park (grass)
Banerjee et al., 2023	Bardhama, West Bengal, India	Forest (trees)
Braun et al., 2023	U.S.A.	Parks, Roadside, Open space, Residential (grass)
Clos et al., 2023	Hartford, Connecticut, U.S.A.	Roadside, Residential (grass)
de Matos et al., 2023	Barcarena, Para, Brazil	Residential, Open Space, Industrial (grass)
Ding et al., 2023	China	Industrial, Residential, Open Space, Park (grass, shrub, tree)
Golia, 2023	Volos and Thessaloniki, Thessaly, Greece	Open Space (grass)
Li et al., 2023	Ningbo, Zhejiang, China	Industrial, Residential, Open Space, Park, Forest (grass, shrub, tree)
Martin et al., 2023	Auckland, Auckland, New Zealand	Open spaces, forests (grass, shrubs, trees)
McGrath et al., 2023	Ontario, Canada	NA

Table 1 (continued)

Authors	Location	Land use and vegetation type
Tessler et al., 2023	Cranbury, New Jersey, U.S.A.	Residential (grass)
Tóth et al., 2023	Budapest, Pest, Hungary	Forests, parks and open spaces (grass, shrubs, trees)
Wang et al., 2023	Yancheng, Jiangsu, China	Forests, parks and open spaces (grass, shrubs, trees)
Aguirre-Alberto & Jaramillo-López, 2024	Morelia, Michoacan, Mexico	Open space, Residential (grass, shrub, tree)
Anuradha, 2024	Madurai, Tamil Nadu, India	Industrial, Residential (grass, shrub, tree)
Burton et al., 2024	United Kingdom	Residential (grass, shrub)
Chou et al., 2024	Saint Paul, Minnesota, U.S.A.	Parks, Residential, Open spaces (grass)
Clos & Chrysochoou, 2024	Hartford, Connecticut, U.S.A.	Parks, Roadside, Open space, Residential (grass)
Hiura et al., 2024	Tomakomai, Hokkaido, Japan	Forest (trees)
Jordanova et al., 2024	Sofia, Sofia District, Bulgaria	Parks (grass)
Korneykova et al., 2024	Murmansk, Murmansk Oblast, Russia	Industrial, Residential, Open spaces, Parks, Roadside (grass)
McDaniel et al., 2024	Iowa City, Iowa, U.S.A.	Industrial, Residential (grass)
Pereira et al., 2024a	Vilnius, Vilnius District, Lithuania	Residential, Open spaces (grass)
Pereira et al., 2024b	Vilnius, Vilnius District, Lithuania	Residential, Open spaces (grass)
Rijk et al., 2024	Helsingborg, Scania, Sweden	Industrial, Residential (grass)
Séré et al., 2024	France, Switzerland, Spain	Open spaces, Parks, Roadsides, Residential (grass, shrub, tree)
Sillo et al., 2024	Prato, Tuscany, Italy	Forest, Park (grass, tree)
Urbaniak et al., 2024	Łódź, Łódź, Poland	Open Space (grass, shrub, tree)
Zandybay et al., 2024	Astana, Aqmola, Kazakhstan	Residential, Open spaces, Industrial, Parks, Roadside (grass)
Zhao et al., 2024a	Central Yunnan and Yangtze River Delta, Yunnan / Yangtze River Delta, China	Industrial, Residential, Open Spaces, Parks, Forest (grass, shrub, tree)
Zhao et al., 2024b	Perth, Western Australia, Australia	Open spaces, Parks (grass)
Rompato et al., 2025	Florence, Tuscany, Italy	Open spaces (trees)
Samani et al., 2025	Tehran, Tehran District, Iran	Parks (grass)
Yee et al., 2025	Greater Baltimore Metropolitan Region, Maryland, U.S.A.	Roadsides, Parks, Open spaces, Industrial (grass)

Deram, 2014). Phytoremediation in particular has been widely investigated as a cost-effective and environmentally friendly alternative, relying on metal-hyperaccumulating species, intercropping and microbial inoculation to degrade, stabilize or extract pollutants.

Yet, despite extensive research, this method has only rarely been translated into practice due to slow remediation rates, site-specific variability and high costs (Balacco et al., 2023; Gómez-sagasti et al., 2021; Yee et al., 2025).

Other approaches have been more directly applied. The "Scoop & Dump" method, for instance, which consists of breaking up compacted urban soils, incorporating compost and applying mulch annually, has been shown in real-world applications to improve soil structure, aeration and microbial activity over the long term (Sax et al., 2017). Similarly, soil amendments such as biochar and peat have demonstrated potential for contaminant immobilization and improvements in microbial activity, although sometimes at the expense of plant nutrient uptake (Rijk et al., 2024). Chemically modified diatomite has also produced promising results, significantly reducing the bioavailability of heavy metals and enhancing enzymatic activity in experimental contexts

Fig. 3. Sampling depth visualization of 51 articles that specified sampling depths. [Streeter & Schilling \(2018\)](#) and [Seboko et al. \(2021\)](#) sampled at depths greater than 120 cm, which was set as the threshold for data visualization in the graph. [Pike et al. \(2021\)](#) used probes at fixed depths, which is why their data are represented as lines rather than bars.

([Samani et al., 2025](#)).

Research gaps

Although progress has been made in understanding pollution pathways and testing remediation techniques, several critical gaps remain. Chief among them is the lack of standardized indicators for SH. Current frameworks assess pollutant removal but do not adequately capture long-term soil functionality or the provision of ecosystem services, making it difficult to compare or evaluate remediation efforts across contexts ([Gómez-sagasti et al., 2021](#)).

Scaling up promising approaches is also a major challenge. While phytoremediation and microbe-assisted strategies are well studied, their slow rates, site-specific effectiveness and limited cost-efficiency prevent widespread application. Likewise, soil amendments such as biochar or diatomite show short-term promise but require further evaluation of long-term environmental effects, trade-offs for soil biota and plants, and economic feasibility. Hybrid methods that integrate physical, biological and chemical remediation have been suggested as a way forward but remain largely experimental ([Séré et al., 2008](#)).

Finally, emerging contaminants require greater attention. VOCs show potential as bioindicators of soil microbial activity, but their integration into monitoring frameworks remains incomplete. Similarly, the dynamics of antibiotic pollution, which differ regionally depending on both soil properties and anthropogenic inputs, are not yet well understood ([Zhao et al., 2024a](#)). Addressing these gaps will require interdisciplinary collaboration, bringing together soil scientists, agronomists, urban planners and policymakers to develop standardized, scalable and sustainable frameworks capable of tackling the complexity of urban soil pollution.

4.2. Soil health assessment

Current knowledge

Studies on urban SH highlight the complexity of this dynamic system, which is shaped not only by ecological processes but also by its role in human well-being, particularly in public spaces such as parks, forests and green areas ([Wang et al., 2018](#)). One of the primary challenges in assessing SH is the high degree of spatial heterogeneity in urban soils, resulting from interactions between organic matter input, pollutant deposition and historical land-use change ([Naylo et al., 2019](#); [Pouyat et al., 2007](#); [Gómez-Brandón et al., 2022](#); [Shi et al., 2008](#); [Streeter & Schilling, 2018](#)). This variability is expressed in enzymatic activity, microbial composition, bulk density, nutrient availability and contamination levels across land uses, reflecting the complex and site-specific nature of urban soils ([Joimel et al., 2016](#); [Zandybay et al., 2024](#)). Understanding these spatial patterns is therefore critical for effective

management and monitoring of SH, since they directly influence soil functioning and ecosystem services.

Microbial communities play a particularly important role as bio-indicators of SH. Bacterial diversity tends to follow more consistent, land-use-dependent patterns ([Naylo et al., 2019](#)), while fungal communities are more variable and sensitive to changing soil conditions ([Gómez-Brandón et al., 2022](#)). In urban green spaces, microbial composition contributes significantly to soil fertility and nutrient cycling; for instance, urban park soils often harbour rich bacterial diversity with functional genes linked to nitrogen, phosphorus and sulphur cycles ([Wang et al., 2018](#)). However, these communities can shift under anthropogenic stressors such as irrigation, fertilization or pesticide application, highlighting their dynamic responses to management practices ([Sapkota et al., 2021](#)). Soil fauna also serve as useful indicators: the pill bug (*Armadillidium vulgare*), for example, responds predictably to variations in organic matter, pH and moisture, while nematode and microbial communities in riparian soils are sensitive to heavy metal contamination, making them effective markers of pollution hotspots ([Aguirre-Alberto & Jaramillo-López, 2024](#); [Wang et al., 2023](#)).

Soil compaction represents another major factor affecting urban SH. By reducing porosity, infiltration and gas exchange, compaction limits plant growth and microbial activity ([Hiura et al., 2024](#); [Pease et al., 2022](#); [Rompato et al., 2025](#); [Séré et al., 2008](#)). Compacted soils in urban and periurban forests have been shown to reduce microbial multifunctionality, which correlates with lower tree richness and biomass accumulation, underlining the strong aboveground–belowground linkages in forested environments ([Hiura et al., 2024](#)). Remediation strategies, particularly the use of organic amendments such as municipal compost or chipped cork, have demonstrated the capacity to alleviate compaction, improving soil respiration, moisture retention and enzymatic activity. These interventions are already applied in practice and point to the potential of organic amendments to strengthen the resilience of urban soils against anthropogenic pressures ([Hiura et al., 2024](#); [Pease et al., 2022](#); [Rompato et al., 2025](#); [Séré et al., 2008](#)).

In terms of assessment methodologies, multiple approaches have been developed, though they often yield contrasting results. The Cornell Soil Health Test (CSHT), for example, places greater emphasis on biological indicators, whereas the Improved Soil Environmental Quality Evaluation (ISEQE) model incorporates urban-specific factors such as compaction, contamination and soil sealing, making it more suitable for urban settings ([Sefati et al., 2019](#)). Recent efforts to design standardized SH scoring systems have proposed nine core soil functions, with reference frameworks built from empirical data collected across several European cities ([Séré et al., 2024](#)). In this study, relevant soil indicators were identified through field descriptions, *in situ* measurements, and

Table 2

Soil health parameters divided into chemical properties (including basic soil properties; soil contaminants are highlighted in bold), biological properties, physical properties, soil–plant proxies connected to one or more ecosystem services (proxies) and indicators spotted in the selected papers. Abbreviations: PAHs = polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons; MBC = microbial biomass carbon; MBN = microbial biomass nitrogen; H' = Shannon index; R' = Rarefied richness; D' = Simpson index.

Paper	Chemical properties	Biological properties	Physical properties	Proxies of one or more Ecosystem services	Indexes
Shi et al., 2008	SOM; TN; AN; TP; AP; pH; EC	invertase; urease; acid phosphatase; catalase	Clay (< 0.01 mm) content		
Chen et al., 2015	pH; SOM; TN; AP; EC; sodium adsorption rate; Bo; As; Cd; Cr; Cu; Pb; Zn	MBC; urease; alkaline phosphatase; invertase; dehydrogenase; catalase	Total porosity		
Harvey et al., 2016 Howard et al., 2016	Sb; As; Cd; Pb; Zn EC; pH		moisture content; penetrability; magnetic susceptibility		Anthropogenic map index
Rahman et al., 2016 Sax et al., 2017	AC; N; SOM; P; K; Fe; Mg; Mn; pH; Zn		bulk density; soil resistance; texture; available water holding capacity; aggregate stability		Cornell soil health test (CSHT)
Çomakli et al., 2018 Streeter & Schilling, 2018 Wang et al., 2018	Pb; Zn; Ni; Cu; Cr; Cd P; SOM; N; TC; C/N		texture		H'; D'; abundance-based coverage estimator index; Chao1 index
Bandowe et al., 2019	\sum 29 PAHs; \sum 15 oxygenated PAHs; inorganic C; SOC; TC	MBC; basal respiration		leaf area index; plant species richness, aboveground plant biomass	inverse D'
Pleshakova et al., 2019	Cu; Zn; Pb; Cd; Cr; Ni	heterotrophic microorganisms; hydrocarbon-oxidizing microorganisms; iron-oxidizing microorganisms; dehydrogenase; catalase; peroxidase; invertase			Total contamination coefficient
Sefati et al., 2019	pH; EC; AP; K; CaCO ₃ ; sodium adsorption rate; soil salinity; exchangeable sodium percentage; SOM; AC; Pb; Cd; Ni; Fe; Zn; Cu; Mn		bulk density; aggregate stability; penetration resistance; Texture		Cornell soil health test; improved soil environmental quality evaluation
Gurjar et al., 2020	pH; EC; SOM; AN; AP; AK; sodium adsorption rate; residual sodium carbonate; Zn; Mn; Cu; Fe; Cr; Ni; Pb; Cd				
Yu et al., 2020			soil moisture; soil temperature; light intensity		
Bandowe et al., 2021 Buzzard et al., 2021	pH; SOM; \sum 29 PAHs; \sum 16 US-EPA PAHs pH; EC; SOM; Gibbs free energy	soil microbial richness	soil temperature; soil volumetric water content; water holding capacity; bulk density		H'
Downey et al., 2021 Galle et al., 2021	total C content; carbon density water-soluble organic C; water-soluble nitrate; solvita labile amino nitrogen; pH; P; K; TC; EC	solvita CO ₂ burst; active fungi; active bacteria	water stable aggregates; bulk density; soil luminance	carbon sequestration NDVI; NDRE	Soil health score
Pike et al., 2021			soil compaction; soil moisture		
Sapkota et al., 2021 Savanoor et al., 2021	pH; SOM; Soil Salinity; N; P; K; CEC pH; EC; SOM; CaCO ₃ ; cation exchange capacity; Zn; Cu; Cd; Cr; Pb; Ni; Co	MBC; MBN; microbial abundance; microbial structure; MBC:MBN	texture		
Seboko et al., 2021	SOM		bulk density	carbon sequestration	

(continued on next page)

Table 2 (continued)

Paper	Chemical properties	Biological properties	Physical properties	Proxies of one or more Ecosystem services	Indexes
Gómez-sagasti et al., 2021	total petroleum hydrocarbons C10–C40; total polychlorinated biphenyls; polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons	β -glucosidase; β -glucosaminidase; arylsulfatase; acid phosphatase; L-Ala-aminopeptidase; L-Leu-aminopeptidase; basal respiration; substrate-induced respiration; substrate consumption activity		plant leaf measurements (e.g. biomass dry weight)	R'; Pielou's evenness; H'; overall enzyme activity
Ward et al., 2021	pH; TC; TN; C stocks	active microbial biomass	water holding capacity; bulk density; texture		
Abu-Shanab et al., 2022		mycelium growth rate; basal respiration		plant measurements (e.g. fresh weight; dry weight; shoot dry weight)	
Gómez-Brandón et al., 2022	pH; TN; TC; AN; AP; C/N	α -glucosidases; β -glucosidases; cellobiohydrolase; xylosidase; β -galactosidase; α -glucuronidase; serin-like protease; chitinase; leucine-aminopeptidase; alkaline phosphomonoesterases; acid phosphomonoesterases; phytase; arylsulfatase; basal respiration	Texture		H'
Pease et al., 2022	pH; EC; N			percent green cover	
Schwarz et al., 2022			soil wetness	NDVI	
Ahmad & Rizvi, 2023		root AMF colonization; phosphatase		root dry mass; shoot dry mass; root/shoot ratio	
Balacco et al., 2023					Decomposition quotient
Banerjee et al., 2023			volumetric water content	carbon sequestration rate	
Braun et al., 2023					
Clos et al., 2023	N; SOM; Pb; Cr; Se; As; Ni; Cu; Zn		clay content		
de Matos et al., 2023	cation exchange capacity; SOM; pH; As; Ba; Pb; Co; Cu; Cr; Hg; Ni; Zn				
Ding et al., 2023	C:N; N; SOM; N density		bulk density		
Golia, 2023	CaCO ₃ ; N; K; P; Ca; Mg; Na; C/N; pH; EC; SOM; Cu; Cd; Pb; Zn	metabolic quotient qCO ₂ ; microbial quotient qMic; MBC	texture; bulk density; soil moisture; water holding capacity		
Li et al., 2023					Risk index of soil pathogens
Martin et al., 2023	$\delta^{13}C$; $\delta^{15}N$; 65 elements				
McGrath et al., 2023					
Tessler et al., 2023	pH; exchange acidity; SOM; P; K; Ca; Mg; Na; NO ₃ ⁻ ; Al; Zn				Species richness; H'
Tóth et al., 2023	SOM; pH; saturation %, total N %; C/N; CaCO ₃ ; Cd; Co; Hg; Ni; Zn	abundance of arthropod groups; total density; taxa richness		EVI	Heavy metal pollution index; urban intensity; Hill's number; QBS-ar; QBS-ab; soil faunal quality index; Acari/Collembola ratio
Wang et al., 2023	EC; pH; AP; AN; SOM; TC; TN	number of pill bugs; body length; body weight	water capacity	number of plant species; vegetation coverage	
Aguirre-Alberto & Jaramillo-López, 2024	N; SOM; pH; As; Cd; Cr; Pb	total fungi; total bacteria; AMF; nematodes	bulk density; soil moisture; porosity; soil color		
Anuradha, 2024	N; P; K; pH; EC; SOM			leaf litter; wood litter; mixed; Twigs; total litter	
Burton et al., 2024	CaCO ₃ ; SOM	total earthworm abundance	texture; soil moisture; soil color		
Chou et al., 2024	P; K; Mg; Fe; Mn; SOM; pH; Zn; Al; Ca; Cu; S; Bo	basal respiration; AMF	aggregate stability; water holding capacity		Soil health score; R'; H'
Clos & Chrysochoou, 2024	Pb				

(continued on next page)

Table 2 (continued)

Paper	Chemical properties	Biological properties	Physical properties	Proxies of one or more Ecosystem services	Indexes
Hiura et al., 2024	pH; EC; N; SOM; TC; C/N	average well color development	bulk density; water content	tree density; basal area; relative growth rate	D'; species diversity
Jordanova et al., 2024	pH; P; Ca; Mg; Mn; Cu; Pb; Zn; Cd; Al; Fe; Ti; Ni; Co; Cr		magnetic susceptibility		Multi-element Pollution Load Index; mineral magnetic indicator
Korneykova et al., 2024	pH; TN; SOM; AP; TC; AK; Ni; Cu; Pb; Zn; Cd; Co	microorganisms ribosomal genes number; microbial biomass; spores number	bulk density		
McDaniel et al., 2024	N; P; K; CEC; pH; SOM	MBC; MBN; MBC:MBN	bulk density; pore space; water-filled pore space; water infiltration rate; time-to-runoff soil penetration		
Pereira et al., 2024a Pereira et al., 2024b				Dandelion flowers	
Rijk et al., 2024	pH; cation exchange capacity; Na; Ca; K; Mg; P; PAHs; $\delta^{13}C$; As; Ba; Cd; Co; Cr; Cu; Hg; Ni; Pb; Zn; Mo; Sb	MBC; basal respiration; substrate-induced respiration; N cycling microbial species		leaf N; leaf $\delta^{15}N$; above ground biomass; root biomass	
Séré et al., 2024	TOC; SOM; EC; cation exchange capacity; C/N; pH; $CaCO_3$; P; Ca; K; Mg; Mn; Na; active limestone; Al; Fe; trace elements; total organic pollutants	microbial and fungi biomass; enzymatic activities; presence of anecic worms; earthworm density	soil depth; color; structure; texture; coarse element content; slope	vegetation cover; root depth	diversity of biological communities
Sillo et al., 2024	volatile organic compounds; cation exchange capacity; P; N; Ca; Mg; Na; K; pH; EC; SOM		texture		Chao1 index; H'; Bray-Curtis index
Urbaniak et al., 2024		average well colour development			H'; substrate richness; substrate evenness
Zandybay et al., 2024 Zhao et al., 2024a	N; AP; AK; AS; SOM; pH; Ca; Mg; Cl; SO; HCO; Pb; Cd; Cr; Ni SOM; Tetracycline; oxytetracycline; chlortetracycline; doxycycline; ofloxacin; lomefloxacin; ciprofloxacin; enrofloxacin; norfloxacin		texture; bulk density; surface temperature soil thickness; saturated hydraulic conductivity; clay content		
Zhao et al., 2024b	N; pH; EC; P; K; cation exchange capacity; SOM; C/N; Zn; Cu; Pb; Cd	MBC	bulk density; maximum water-holding capacity; water stable aggregates soil temperature; soil humidity; texture	carbon density	
Rompato et al., 2025	pH; AP; SOM; TN	CO ₂ emissions; H ₂ O emissions; basal respiration; urease; protease; acid phosphomonoesterase; alkaline phosphomonoesterase; β -glucosidase; arylsulfatase	texture; specific surface area		
Samani et al., 2025	pH; EC; SOM; calcium carbonate equivalent; cation exchange capacity; Pb; Zn; Cu	urease; dehydrogenase; alkaline phosphatase	texture; specific surface area		
Yee et al., 2025	pH; SOM; Al; As; Cd; Cu; Cr; Fe; Pb; Zn	soil microarthropod abundance	bulk density	shoot and root Al, As, Cd, Cu, Cr, Fe, Pb, Zn	Acari/Collembola ratio; metal contamination index

laboratory analyses, and integrated into a scoring system based on four reference classes (0–3) for each soil function. This study shows that sealed and brownfield soils consistently rank lowest, while urban parks achieve the highest scores, offering a preliminary yet adaptable framework for comparative assessment. Nonetheless, the application of these scoring methods remains limited, reflecting the relatively recent emergence of urban SH as a dedicated research field.

Research gaps

Despite significant progress, major challenges continue to hinder the effective assessment of urban SH. The high spatial heterogeneity of urban soils complicates the identification of reliable and universally applicable indicators, while the dynamic nature of microbial and faunal communities introduces further variability. Although microbial and faunal bioindicators have proven valuable, their responses to

management practices and contamination stressors remain insufficiently understood, particularly in the long term.

A further gap lies in addressing soil compaction, which remains one of the most pervasive forms of urban soil degradation. While organic amendments have shown promise in reversing compaction effects, more research is needed to establish best practices for their application, especially under different soil types, land uses and contamination scenarios.

Assessment frameworks for SH are still in development. Although recent models, such as CSHT, ISEQE and standardized scoring systems, have advanced the field, there is no consensus on which indicators most effectively capture the complexity of SH in urban environments. Moreover, few of these tools have been systematically applied across cities and regions. Future work should therefore prioritize the integration of

Fig. 4. Distribution of the selected articles by thematic focus. The categories include Ecosystem services, Stakeholder surveys and policies, Soil pollution and remediation, Water management and green infrastructure, and Soil Health assessment. (For interpretation of the references to color in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the web version of this article.)

physical, chemical and biological indicators into standardized scoring frameworks, ideally combined with geospatial approaches and bio-indicators, to provide more comprehensive and comparable insights into the functioning and resilience of urban soils.

4.3. Ecosystem services

Current knowledge

Urban SH underpins ecological functions and ESs that are essential for sustaining green spaces (FAO, 2015). These services contribute directly to improved air and water quality, positively influencing urban nature and, in turn, the well-being of city inhabitants (Brevik et al., 2018). Furthermore, recently ESs were a primary driver of descaling projects (Vieillard et al., 2024). Among the most significant services provided by urban soils is carbon sequestration. In cities, where human activities elevate carbon levels, the capacity of soils to act as carbon sinks becomes particularly important (Zhao et al., 2024b). Urban forests represent a key opportunity for carbon storage, although optimizing this potential depends heavily on the site's history and local characteristics (Downey et al., 2021). Urban lawns can also store carbon, but their contribution is offset by maintenance practices that reduce biodiversity and release emissions, thereby undermining some of the intended benefits. Recent work suggests that transforming lawns into semi-natural habitats, such as meadows, can simultaneously improve SH, enhance biodiversity, and increase carbon storage potential (Tessler et al., 2023).

Flood regulation is also an important ES, although it is highly dependent on local soil conditions and management practices. Green spaces such as lawns can mitigate flood impacts, but their effectiveness is strongly influenced by compaction and maintenance intensity. Soil penetration resistance has been used successfully as a proxy for flood retention capacity, revealing substantial variability within and between lawns (Pereira et al., 2024a). This function is also highly dynamic, fluctuating with seasonal changes in soil moisture, which highlights the need for continuous assessment.

The provision of ESs in urban soils is further complicated by spatial variability, a challenge that mirrors difficulties observed in soil health assessment. Soils surrounding roadside trees, for example, are often subject to compaction and debris accumulation, producing highly site-specific responses (Galle et al., 2021). Tools that can detect and quantify such disturbances are therefore critical for accurately modelling and

assessing ES delivery.

Recent studies emphasize that urban soils support a wide range of services beyond carbon storage and flood regulation, including pollination and biodiversity enhancement. However, the effectiveness of these services is consistently shaped by site conditions, land-use history, and ongoing management practices. While methods for quantifying ESs are improving, much of their application in urban settings remains limited, reflecting the relatively recent recognition of the importance of urban soils in delivering ecological and social benefits (O'Riordan et al., 2021).

Research gaps

Although research has demonstrated the value of urban soils in supporting ESs, several key gaps persist. A major challenge is understanding how these services evolve over time under varying land-use histories, management practices and soil contexts. For carbon sequestration, in particular, there is a need for long-term studies that consider how storage capacity develops across different soil types and under changing environmental pressures (Downey et al., 2021; Pouyat & Trammell, 2019). Similarly, the capacity of urban soils to regulate floods requires further exploration, particularly in relation to compaction dynamics, seasonal moisture changes and spatial variability within green spaces.

More broadly, there is still no standardized framework for assessing the wide spectrum of ESs provided by urban soils. While progress has been made in quantifying individual services, integrated models that combine biological, chemical and physical parameters are still lacking. Such models are essential for producing more accurate and comparable assessments across different urban contexts.

Future research should prioritize ESs with direct implications for human health, such as those related to air and water quality regulation, biodiversity maintenance and climate mitigation (Baveye et al., 2016; Dominati et al., 2010). Addressing these gaps will ensure a more comprehensive understanding of the multifaceted value of urban soils and strengthen their role in sustainable urban planning.

4.4. Water management and green infrastructure

Current knowledge

The increasing use of reclaimed water for irrigating urban green areas has brought attention to its potential impacts on SH (Chen et al., 2015; Rahman et al., 2016). In some contexts, reclaimed water can enhance SH by increasing soil organic matter, total nitrogen, and available phosphorus compared to tap water (Chen et al., 2015). Yet, it also carries risks, including heavy metal and salt accumulation, increased sodicity, and reduced hydraulic conductivity, all of which are indicators of soil degradation (Chen et al., 2015; Rahman et al., 2016). Ultimately, the safety and effectiveness of reclaimed water irrigation depend on site-specific conditions and management practices. When properly managed, reclaimed water can support soil functions and urban vegetation, but without safeguards, it may compromise long-term soil health.

Complementary to water reuse, green infrastructure (GI) practices, such as rain gardens and water harvesting, have gained recognition as effective tools to restore ecological functions and support ecosystem services (Buzzard et al., 2021). GI has the capacity to counterbalance negative effects of reclaimed water use while simultaneously promoting more sustainable urban water management. Within this context, Nature-Based Solutions (NBS) have shown particular promise. Recent studies demonstrate that NBS can enhance soil microbial diversity and resilience, increasing microbial activity and positively influencing biodiversity (Urbaniak et al., 2024). Seasonal variability further shapes microbial functional diversity, highlighting the dynamic nature of SH responses to NBS implementation.

Research gaps

Despite these advances, significant knowledge gaps remain in understanding how GI and water management practices influence SH over

time. While rain gardens, water harvesting, and NBS have been studied, other GI strategies, such as green and blue corridors, remain underexplored in relation to soil processes, despite their importance for urban regeneration and ecological connectivity (Li et al., 2015). Similarly, the long-term implications of reclaimed water irrigation are not fully understood, particularly concerning cumulative contaminant loads, seasonal microbial shifts, and soil–plant interactions.

Research gaps remain in the integration of water management and GI within a unified soil health framework, particularly the lack of standardized assessment tools that connect SH indicators with reclaimed water use, NBS, and other GI practices. These gaps limit understanding of their combined impacts on microbial diversity, soil resilience, and ecosystem service delivery, constraining the ability of urban water management strategies to both conserve resources and sustain soil functioning.

5. Future perspective and conclusions

Urban soils require urgent attention, demanding re-prioritization in policies and funding. This starts with an increased observation of urban soils focusing on comprehensive, interdisciplinary data collection, followed by investigations into the causes and processes affecting urban soils to develop sustainable solutions. Equally urgent is the need to confront the research gaps that hinder such progress. Current studies remain skewed toward chemical properties, overlooking physical, biological, and ecosystem service dimensions vital to human well-being. Reliance on topsoil sampling further limits insight, as deeper layers play a critical role in ecosystem services. Future studies must adopt a whole-profile perspective and fully leverage ecosystem services to advance understanding of urban soil health.

To assess and monitor SH in urban environments, remote sensing and proximal sensing techniques have gained increasing attention as effective and scalable tools. Field-based methods such as electrical conductivity (EC) and magnetic susceptibility (MS) have shown potential to differentiate anthropogenic soils and assess contamination levels, though their accuracy is often constrained by vegetation cover, compaction, and the presence of artifacts, requiring laboratory validation (Howard et al., 2016; Jordanova et al., 2024). Magnetic indicators, such as MS, have also been proposed as proxies for soil contamination, correlating with heavy metal pollution and urbanization intensity (Howard et al., 2016). More recently, emerging technologies including GIS-based soil mapping, *in situ* sensor systems such as the Plant Spike (Yu et al., 2020), and portable X-ray fluorescence (pXRF) devices (Clos & Chrysochoou, 2024) provide real-time, cost-effective, and reliable approaches for detecting contamination and monitoring soil properties across urban landscapes (Anuradha, 2024). Coupled with geostatistical modelling, these tools enhance spatial resolution and allow continuous tracking of soil functions over time, thereby supporting adaptive management strategies.

As urbanization accelerates, the intersection of soil science, policy, and stakeholder engagement emerges as a critical nexus for sustainable urban development. In fact, a significant communication gap exists between soil scientists and urban stakeholders, including policymakers, urban planners, and the public. Bridging this communication gap is essential to developing research agendas and policies that effectively address the unique challenges and needs of urban communities (Schwarz et al., 2022). Improved and inclusive collaboration can result in more actionable solutions for enhancing SH in urban settings. Citizen science initiatives, despite challenges with participant engagement, offer a promising way to raise public awareness and generate valuable soil ecosystem data (Burton et al., 2024).

The importance of adopting systematic, proactive soil management practices, rather than reactive approaches, in urban contexts is crucial for long-term soil sustainability across urban ecosystems (McGrath et al., 2023). The transition from the planner's focus on the "soil surface" to the soil scientist's perspective of the "living soil volume" can be realized

if urban soils, beyond their economically valuable surface area, reveal more of their functional depth over time. Soil is first and foremost made visible through a field approach, using a holistic pedological approach that includes the physico-chemical properties and biological activity of soils. Dialogue between stakeholders and action to preserve healthy urban soils will be enabled by the dynamics of living labs (*sensu* EU Mission Soil, <https://mission-soil-platform.ec.europa.eu/living-labs>). This new way of working together, closely involving civil society and all its stakeholders alongside researchers on demonstration sites, will provide examples of success stories, to lead the transition to healthy soils as quickly as possible. Soil quality and health measurement networks that are well developed in rural areas should ideally be extended to cities, including a soil monitoring programme to inform stakeholders so that better account is taken of soil in planning strategies (Blanchart et al., 2019). Soils will need to find their place in a circular urban metabolism, via soil engineering and the thoughtful use of urban resources. Giving soil a prominent place in cities will then be a guarantee of transformation and transition towards more resilient and sustainable cities. This will not happen without involving citizens through education, training and communication, and by making citizen science even more attractive. The challenge before us is to go beyond the presumed complexity of urban soils, to make them tangible and comprehensible to everyone, and above all to convince as many people as possible that the health of (urban) soils and the health of human beings are intimately linked.

Declaration of Generative AI and AI-assisted technologies in the writing process

During the preparation of this work the authors used ChatGPT (OpenAI) in order to improve language and readability of the text. After using this tool, the authors reviewed and edited the content as needed and take full responsibility for the content of the publication.

CRediT authorship contribution statement

Michelangelo Vuono: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Methodology, Formal analysis, Conceptualization. **Domenico Paolo Di Leonardo:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Project administration, Funding acquisition. **Christophe Schwartz:** Writing – review & editing, Funding acquisition. **Fabio Terribile:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Methodology, Funding acquisition, Conceptualization.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

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